

SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL TRAINING SYSTEM FOR SOFTWARE DEVELOPMENT BASED ON "TRIPLE MANAGEMENT"

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Abstract

As it students were unable to meet the software industry's demand for skilled personnel, a tripartite managed 3D software development hands-on training system was proposed aimed at improving software development capabilities and developing a student's sense of innovation. This system can effectively increase student interest in software development, as well as instill a sense of practical skills and innovation, providing a solid foundation after graduation for students to quickly integrate into the software development process that meets the needs of the software industry.

Keywords: triple management, practical teaching, software, software development, student engagement, hands-on learning, programming education, industry readiness.

Introduction

Currently, employment of college graduates has become a well-known Social problem in China. In particular, the employment status of it specialists, computer specialists as representatives, is more severe. At the same time, the demand of the software industry for talent is also facing significant difficulties. A dilemma emerged in the software industry that "it is difficult for graduates to find jobs and difficult for software companies to recruit". This dilemma was related to the curriculum system, most notably the professional practical teaching system and the management mechanism[1-2]. Fundamentally speaking, the background of higher education in China is still a kind of replica to reflect the large-scale industrial production, which emphasizes standardization and characteristics.

According to China'S IT education and training situation, a number of studies have done this paper to improve the practical ability and sense of innovation in software design of students. Subtle guidance of incentives was created and a three-dimensional

applied learning platform was created to prepare software development skills, which stimulated the driving force of research for professional knowledge and software design, increased students' enthusiasm for innovation, prepared excellent software development talents.

To address this gap, educational reform efforts are increasingly focused on developing practical, industry-aligned skills among software engineering students. Traditional curricula, often theoretical and detached from hands-on application, do not sufficiently prepare students for the demands of modern software development. By incorporating structured, practice-oriented approaches, universities can cultivate students' technical skills, adaptability, and innovation—qualities essential for professional success in an evolving industry. The 'triple management' model proposed in this study offers a framework that emphasizes sustained engagement and skill-building through progressive stages, ultimately equipping students with a comprehensive foundation in both theoretical knowledge and applied practice.

The main system for the development of "triple management" software

A "three-step" multi-stream advanced software development system was created with the aim of exploring the possibilities of software development of basic requirements, studying the ability to develop software. The so-called "Three-driven" means the following three "driven". First, in the first year of the students who studied the program, an "interest-based" practical method was used. Basic practical installation quality was adopted to add independent foundation for the software and basic reading of ordinary game writing students[3-4]. The ACM software program of the requirements for the study of the main course in the second, second and third courses of requirements, and the Ministry of software for participation in the competition, provided practical assistance "based on the choice" in it. This information includes only knowledge on the design of programs and algorithms, from the need for a huge amount of information. It has the characteristics of a past limit, but greater depth, which is very suitable for creating software for the requirements of these competitions and learning to analyze and design algorithms. These competitions can learn the inner strength of the student in order to achieve success with the development of software in the future. Thirdly, in the third and fourth year of the head of the study of vocational courses, students have a wide range of measures. The requirements adopted a "project-based" method of practice for the possibility of involvement in the development of a practical research project. Opportunities were created close to the right practice to the requirements, which plays an important role for students to have a firm understanding of professional knowledge and access to software development work in its field.

"Three-driven" practical educational system educational and cognitive requirements education in the educational and educational system, at the beginning of the type it is considered the features and problems proposed by individual students, corresponding to the psychological transformation process of the requirements. "The three-sided system has confirmed the content of the pensioner, which may have increased independently. Specific topics of research include the creation and implementation of the following three platforms.

This 'triple management' approach not only enhances the technical proficiency of students but also nurtures essential soft skills like teamwork, problem-solving, and project management. By engaging students at different stages, from sparking initial interest to advanced project work, the system ensures a gradual and supportive development path. Each stage is carefully structured to reinforce previous learning while introducing new, relevant challenges that reflect real-world software development practices. Moreover, this system encourages students to take ownership of their learning, fostering independence and a proactive approach to problem-solving. Through its blend of individual projects, competitive coding, and collaborative research, the 'triple management' system seeks to create well-rounded software professionals who are equipped with both the technical and interpersonal skills required by the industry.

Basic training platform" on interests"

The educational goals, methods and desires of freshmen are blurred. If they are not managed on time and efficiently, irreparable damage will be caused to their future education. Thus, the main task of this stage is to create interest in learning. Interest in learning is a positive understanding of an individual's predisposition and emotional state during the learning process. From the point of view of educational psychology, interest is the psychological characteristic of a person who wants to recognize and learn to obtain certain knowledge, an internal force that can motivate people to seek knowledge, which is the motivation to learn, which is the most active and realistic psychological component of interest in learning.[5]. With an interest in the subject, students can continue to focus on learning it and improve academic performance. Therefore, at the beginning of the study of programming, the previous theoretical model of boring audiences was canceled. Instead, interesting examples such as tavla, Othello were included in the teaching. Effective use of these examples will help students understand the practicality of the program, increasing interest in learning. Students with a specific base in the field of programming were able to develop their own simple games to develop basic programming skills in students. In the second and third year, students

were encouraged to develop further in the writing of games by hosting competitions, with students being given a networking platform for games writing competitions. Practical experience has shown that this method can significantly increase students' interest in programming and even turn a passion for games into a passion for composing them. In the third and fourth grades, students acquire sufficient knowledge. They can start trying out a larger and more standardized game design. Students were now offered to join groups, take advantage of free time and even the graduation period to work on design or game design and game testing, a very good professional practice. In short, instead of allowing students to play games from freshman to graduate, it is better to allow them to create games from freshman to graduate.

Currently, at the main stage of teaching Informatics in many universities, there are the following main problems: unreasonable distribution of hours between theoretical and practical classes; very stereotypical class experiences that make it difficult to develop innovative thinking of students; the ability to learn together and lack of Team Spirit, low learning efficiency. In addition, on the one hand, fundamental teaching has been found to be far from practical application - basic learning disciplines such as mathematics, etc. they are far from the practical application of Computer Science, and students have difficulty understanding them. On the other hand, students tend to acquire the latest computer technologies and skills while not liking or even rejecting relatively boring core subjects, especially math courses. Thus, although students are able to master some computer programs and development technologies very well at an early stage, they demonstrate a lack of ability to develop later and do not have knowledge on the main topics.

Project driven” actual development platform

In the present university educational reform, improving students' innovative ability is strongly advocated, and attracting students to take part in the scientific research project is an effective method. Scientific research activities not only help students in expanding their scope of knowledge and building a reasonable knowledge structure, but also can satisfy their high level psychological requirements and increase their confidence of daring to overcome difficulties and risking making breakthroughs. Therefore, scientific research is the only road to cultivate students' modern way of thinking. In this process, teachers come up to students, and develop a harmonious relationship with them. Their instruction is full of original research inspiration and achievement and gives students gradual and imperceptible cultivation and enlightenment; at the same time, students gain the chance to be in intimate contact with teachers, which will further inspire their enthusiasm and desire of exploration and will

be very helpful in cultivating students' innovative ability. To achieve this objective, making students recognize the enjoyment and value of scientific innovation is the key, and on this basis, students are guided to develop their own innovative ability.

Scientific research activities focus on fostering students' self-learning ability and independent operation skills; this arouses students' appetite for knowledge, their comprehensive thinking quality and ability to utilize knowledge comprehensively to solve actual problems, at the same time cultivates students' serious attitude, strict requirement and rigorous style toward scientific knowledge, and really improves manipulating ability and phenomenon observation ability. Scientific research activities add the part for students' manipulating, increase the interest in learning, enhance the understanding between each other, and cultivate students' cooperative spirit, theoretical thinking and innovation ability; they are good for cultivating students' comprehensive ability such as scientific research ability, thinking ability, self-learning ability, manipulating ability, expressing ability and cooperation ability, etc., and they will lay a solid foundation for their future work and further study.

Conculison

This paper is put forward for the first time in the "three driven" practical training system for software development skills. Starting with "driven interest", gradually students promote student autonomy; increase students' "internal strength" through "driven competition"; increase the competitive force of employment through "driven project"; develop software, this three-dimensional classification stereoscopic applied learning system is a set of effective methods for the cultivation of student software development ability. The purpose of Computer Science and related specialties was to allow students of each class to create motivation to learn aimless students through the use of a "three-way managed" practical teaching system, and to allow graduate students to create opportunities to bring their potential to a greater level, and the professional training of administrative personnel was also provided with new ideas of teaching.

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